

DESIGN & EMOTION: ATTACHMENT TO SIGNIFICANT OBJECTS AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted in the field of "Design & Emotion" and consisted of identifying evidence relating to levels of attachment to significant objects among a group of young people from the city of Caruaru, Pernambuco State, Brazil. For this purpose, artefacts from two different periods (childhood and the present day) were addressed. Savaş's methodology (Savaş, 2004) was used to categorize the artefacts. Key aspects to help understand the reasons for attachment and the user: object relationship were identified. It was found that present-day artefacts were of most significance, experience of Use, Utility Function and Form being the principal explanations of attachment relationships among the young people interviewed.

KEYWORDS: *Design, Emotion, Affective Bond, Attachment and Product Affectivity.*

INTRODUCTION

The arrival of the new technologies and industrial processes that characterize the present led to a change in the functionalist paradigm in design. The culture of mass production that predominated at the start of the industrialization process gave way to flexible production techniques that sought to respond to the individuality of the user. In recent years functionality has become implicit in the act of designing, and important new aspects of the design process such as emotional, cultural and social factors have become increasingly necessary and important. Consequently, the user has become the focus of the design process and user needs and aspirations have taken center stage.

In this scenario, other changes have also occurred, especially in the relations between individuals and artefacts. This relationship has become a topic of interest for many researchers in various disciplines, including design, neuroscience, psychology and anthropology. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to understand, first, the individual and then groups of users, in order to address the needs and desires of the latter through the design of artefacts.

Despite the different names that have been given to this relationship in the field of design – for example, Design & Emo-

tion and Experiential Design - the object of study does not change: the emotional competence of products to provide positive user experiences. This approach does not undermine the principle of functionality but refers to the belief that designers should always take emotion into account during the design process. In theory this increases the period of time artefacts remain in the possession of consumers, making it possible to reduce the numbers of products that need to be purchased. However, never in history have human beings possessed so many objects, though their symbolic value is less and less noticed, leading to empty and superficial relationships (Cardoso, 2012).

This phenomenon is due, in part, to what the authors call the ephemerality of the product. Every day, companies release new versions of products, resulting in the creation of new needs, in a process Sudjic has described as a "serial seduction" (Sudjic, 2010). And yet, these artefacts lack durability and cannot resist the continued use they are put to: they are soon replaced by more modern versions. Thus, as a consequence of the short period of contact between user and product, little or no affective attachment develops between them. In contrast, the use of emotional factors in the production of objects leads to growing consumption, creating a significant volume of waste that conflicts with another yearning of the modern consumer: sustainability.

Designers can contribute to solving this problem by recourse to their knowledge of other areas related to emotions, feelings, affection, culture, consumption, etc., seeking solutions that help to design products that are consistent with current realities. This is not a solution to all problems, but a step towards discovering and understanding the motivations behind individual choices.

The current research was conducted in 2012 in the city of Caruaru, Pernambuco State, Brazil. It focuses on understanding the affective bond between young people and objects that were significant to them in their childhoods and/or in the present. Respondents were students in the first semester of the Design course at the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Centro Acadêmico do Agreste.

PRODUCT AFFECTIVITY

In the past, the practical function and utility of the product were key elements for the development of new artefacts. Nowadays, issues such as the meanings assigned by the sensations, perceptions and emotions that objects transmit must be included in new projects.

The current situation points to a need to project beyond the utilitarian sense of a product, so that the user may assign special personal meanings that result from their positive experiences with it. Thus, the meanings attributed to objects are reflected in ideas, values, past experiences, living conditions and future expectations. That is, the meanings given to products as a result of their use arises as a consequence of the relationship between the human being and the object. An artefact that individuals experience as merely functional does not generate any special, emotional, bond (Schifferstein et al, 2004; Cardoso, 2012; Mugge, 2008).

Thus, the affectivity of the product may be defined, according Schifferstein, Mugge & Hekkert (2004), as the strength of the emotional bond that individuals experience as a result of their relationship with a particular object. Emotions can cause either attachment or detachment, depending on the affective reaction the artefact evokes. Savaş (2004, p. 318) defines attachment as "a positive emotional state of the relationship between an individual and a product, which indicates a strong linkage between them." The result of this relationship is that people consider the product to be a part of themselves, and therefore have a strong desire to keep it.

Michael Lacroix argues that the theme of *emotion* is central to these relationships, but the idea that there is an "awakening to affectivity" should be viewed with caution. The author argues that the craving for strong sensations, however ephemeral, is accompanied by an anesthetizing of sensitivity. "We feel lots of emotions, but we don't know how to feel" (Lacroix, 2006, p.11, authors' translation). This happens because modern humans are looking for explosive, instant, experiences of excitement, marked by strong sensations. This phenomenon

is also clearly present in the field of advertising. For example, designers seek to make products that excite the emotions on the understanding that "emotion sells". Lacroix explains that there are two sides to this: "First, [it] shows that a return to emotion is taking place. (...) Second, they warn us, even because of their role in the consumer society, the danger of misuse of emotion" (Lacroix, 2006, p.18, authors' translation). This argument constitutes an effective questioning of emotions, whose consequences may be different from what was originally intended.

Therefore, the building of a strong and positive affective bond between users and products is considered to be a design strategy that might help delay the rapid disposal of a product or its replacement with new versions. This is because individuals tend to keep those products that adequately meet all their needs and which - whether for utilitarian or emotional reasons - promote special meanings for them (Schifferstein et al, 2004; Mugge, 2008; Savaş, 2004).

Savaş (2004, p.318) defines detachment as a "a negative emotional state of the relationship between an individual and a product which indicates the lack of linkage between them", arguing that even if the product works as expected this does not necessarily create a special emotional bond with the user, making its disposal or replacement easier (Mugge, 2008).

Modern humans live, then, in a state of constant emotional stimulus and permanent agitation but are, at the same time, unable to experience authentic feelings. Lacroix (2006, p. 161) affirms that "the cult of emotion can be the best or the worst of things and, often, what we see today is the spectacle of the worst". He concludes that a solution would be to replace the shock-emotions (rapid and short-lived) with contemplation-emotions (linked to memory - durable and more likely to be converted into a sense). This process would imply a need for quality of subject and object (Lacroix, 2006).

It is understandable that individuals may feel attached to people, objects, brands, etc. For products, this attachment occurs at different levels of abstraction, varying according to their nature (Mugge, 2008). Mugge further argues that attachment varies between Specific Products - where the user has an emotional bond with a particular object that does not dissolve if the original object is replaced by an identical one, because of the uniqueness of the context in which the original was purchased or used. A similar phenomenon occurs with so-called General Products, referring to a type of product where others of the same genre, which need not necessarily be physically identical, can be easily replaced.

These issues have a direct influence on the relationship between the product and the individual, and especially the responsibility of the design professional to respond to them. For this, Lacroix (2006, p. 162) suggests, "(...) we must ensure the quality of the objects to which we give our attention. These objects should be elevated, noble, worthy of admiration, without which the contemplative attention we assign them is in unstable equilibrium."

Design and Emotion

In Brazil and in the rest of the world many researchers have argued that the study of emotions and emotional relationships, reactions and responses that characterize the connection between user and product are fundamental to the design process. Thus, Hekkert & McDonagh (2003) argue that emotional responses should be considered at the point when the design goals are set, and not just as a side effect of the main function of the product. The authors add that these emotional reactions are not only derived from the relationship of the user with the product, but the context in which it occurs. This interaction is of great importance to the final experience.

In general, the objective of the Design & Emotion approach is to analyze emotional responses to products and to develop tools and methods that aid in the creation of relationships between products and users (Overbeeke & Hekkert, 1999; Kurtgözü, 2003). Apparently, though, there is no consensus concerning the nomenclature employed. Most authors use terms such as Design & Emotion, though variations exist, such as Emotional Design (Norman, 2004); Pleasure-based Design (Jordan, 2002) and Experience Design (Jääskö et al. 2003). In Brazil, names like *Design Experiencial* (Buccini, 2006), *Design & Emoção* (Damázio, 2006) *Design Emocional* (Iida & Muhlenberg, 2006) have been used.

This paper adopts the term "Design & Emotion", which has been proposed as a field of research in design by the Design & Emotion Society and was presented at the First International Conference on Design & Emotion.

It is well known that there is a proliferation of objects in everyday life that may be considered to form links between people, and act as mediators of actions in life, evoking all sorts of emotions and feelings (Damázio et al., 2008). According to Norman (2004), objects have personal components, which neither designers nor manufacturers can provide, but that exist because of their powers of motivation and meaning. Thus, the meanings of the symbolic function of a product are assigned by users according to an intangible process of personal interpretation (Desmet et al. 2001). Therefore, emotionally relevant objects may be present in memory, as a result of the recovery of the details of the relationship between the user and the product.

The artefacts of memory have been studied by many researchers, including Vera Damázio (2006) and Cristiane Menezes (2007). These authors propose that such artefacts may be considered successful, in as much as they produce a positive relationship between the user and the product, leading to a lasting relationship. The importance of studies that are designed better to understand human emotions and their capabilities and limitations is, then, clear. In the field of design things could not be otherwise, since products are in constant interaction with their human users, and research of this kind will result in more sophisticated products, contributing to a more sustainable future.

PROCEDURE

The paper is based on work submitted as a supplementary requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Design at the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Centro Acadêmico do Agreste. Its aim is to collect and analyze data in order to improve understanding of the affective bond between people and objects that were significant for them either in childhood and/or in the present day.

Because the research is preliminary and exploratory, and not a representative study – though it is based on a significant amount of data – it was necessary to choose a sample to which the instruments of data collection could be applied using semi-structured interviews.

The study was carried out in Caruaru, in the arid zone of Pernambuco, Brazil. The sample was chosen to respond to a series of research questions. Which aspects of objects generate good or bad feelings about them? Are changes in technology and communications key to this emotional bond? Do certain factors that cause good and bad emotions remain independent of technological progress? Are these factors, or some aspects of them, un-bounded by time?

In the light of these questions it was decided to focus the research on first semester students of the Design course at the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco. The sample was made up of randomly selected students enrolled in the first year; and the interviews were conducted during the first weeks of term, thus preventing the answers being influenced by the respondents having received some academic orientation. The final sample was made up of seven young women and two young men, totaling nine respondents, whose ages ranged between 17 and 23.

A second stage of data collection occurred with the application of a semi-structured interview, which explored the issues further. All interviews were duly recorded using a digital camera. The interview was divided into two phases:

- Memories of objects that had a special place in the affective memory of respondents when they were children, particularly those they liked. The same information was gathered for objects respondents currently possessed;
- An introspective exercise to recall sensations, affective memories and aesthetic perceptions about the objects mentioned, in order to gather details of the sensations that provoked respondent views of the objects and made them special.

After the data had been collected, it had to be classified and analyzed. This was done using the methodology proposed by Savaş (2004), for the characterization of data.

According to Savaş it is possible to identify both the *Nature* of the attributes of objects that are related to attachment and detachment and the *Reasons* they function as they do. However, due to the extensive amount of data obtained during the research, in this paper, it is only possible to present a snippet of information provided in the interviews, explaining why

consumers felt attachment. These reasons are divided into 6 groups of attachment: the Past, Experience, Utilitarian Function, Personal Identity, Social Identity and Form.

ANALYSIS

The nine respondents cited 53 products as having produced an attachment relationship in childhood, alongside 44 present-day products that provoke attachment today.

The Past

With this group it is understood that the relationship involves existing lived experiences and memories. The group subdivided into three sub-groups described below. 56.6% of childhood items mentioned had something to do with the past, while for present-day objects the percentage was 46.6%. These results indicate that for childhood objects the past plays a more important role than for present-day objects, since these items are generally obtained as gifts and refer to a person or place.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Family Heirloom: corresponding to gifts from family members. 32.1% of childhood objects were reported as family gifts, while for present-day objects the percentage was 22.2%. This phenomenon presents itself spontaneously. It was observed that respondents tended to explain who they had obtained their special product from, for example:

"It was my uncle who gave it to me, and he died not long after." (Interviewee 5: about a cloth ball)

Memory: related to those objects that resemble a particular person or time. According to the data obtained, this is the biggest reason for items the group, accounting for 41.4% of childhood items, while the total for present-day objects was 42.2%. It was noticed that many of the products have a strong attachment relationship associated with memory, as in the following response:

- "I liked it because my aunt gave it to me the first time I went to her house." (Interviewee 6: about a Patamon doll)

Habitual Ownership: corresponding to those products which respondents have owned or used for a long period of time. The sub-group applied to 15.1% of childhood objects and 26.6% of present-day ones. This can be explained because most respondents had developed a long-term relationship with objects during childhood despite the fact their contact with the object had been fleeting, as explained in the following testimony:

"I got this this shirt when I was tiny: I think my mom gave it to me when I was a baby." (Interviewee 5: about a white shirt)

Experience

Experience consists in the relationship between respondents and the object, i.e., the experience they have when using the

product. Experience may be divided into three sub-groups, described below. 73.6% of childhood artefacts were classified as belonging to this group, compared to 68.9% of present-day objects. In both cases, this was the attribute that most stood out, leading to the conclusion that the sensations arising from this relationship are fundamental for the attachment to objects.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Enjoyment: corresponding to objects that provide pleasure in their use. This was the most important reason, which in childhood objects was obtained by 49% of reported items, a figure that reached 48.9% for present-day objects. When an individual purchases an object they expect it to fulfill its practical function and to provide pleasure in its use. Enjoyment is thus central to the affective relationship, as may be seen from the following testimony:

- "It is interesting that today I feel naked without a cell phone, I feel kind of lost, you know? It is as though my phone were part of me. I have everything I need on it: internet, cell phone, camera, music, games, calendar, etc." (Interviewee 9: on their phone).

Frequent Actions: objects used frequently in daily activities. The respondents reported that 13.2% of childhood items belonged to this sub-group, compared to 42.2% for present-day objects. This large difference is explained by the fact that the need for objects evolves as the individual gets older, as may be seen from the following testimony

- "I mean, everywhere I went, at school, at home, I always took it with me. Like, it was a toy that, if I'm going out, I'll take it" (Interviewee 5: about a cloth ball).

Desirable Feelings: consists of the feelings evoked by the experience of using objects. Respondents tended to explain the feelings that the products generated in various ways. The incidence for childhood items was 45.3% compared to 40% for present-day objects. This is illustrated by the following response:

- "They give me a sense of security: when I use them I feel more capable and less blind." (Interviewee 9: about their glasses)

Utilitarian Function

This group reflects the basic utility of the product and its performance. As with the previous attributes, the group is also divided into three sub-groups, described below. It was observed that for childhood objects, only 5.66% of the items were so classified compared to 48.9% of present-day products. These contrasting figures show that Utilitarian Function plays a key role in attachment to current objects, since use becomes more important, and even essential, over time.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Utility is associated with the needs of users. This attribute was present for 5.66% of childhood objects and 46.6% of present-day ones, demonstrating that in childhood the utility of the product is probably not a reason for attachment. This is illustrated by the following testimony on a present-day item:

"I like it because it is really necessary. I live on the run. My watch helps me with the notion of time... it also brings me security" (Interviewee 2: about his watch).

Performance concerns the ability of artefacts to fulfill their basic function correctly. The respondents did not associate any object from childhood with this attribute compared to 26.6% of present-day products. This data is related to the fact that as they get older young people begin to purchase products that are useful to them and that performance and quality of these products is key to attachment:

"My cell is normal, not big and not small. Its touch screen is quite simple. But it has a wonderful camera!" (Interviewee 2: about their phone)

Tools of Trade are those artefacts that are used for work or to make money. Again, no childhood object was included in this sub-group, against 4.44% for present-day objects. However, as in childhood, present-day objects had little significance, probably because they are still young, or there is no present need. The reason for this is that few children work or engage in activities that have assumed importance in their daily lives:

"Initially it was out of necessity, then I started to like it because, with it, I can do everything associated with photos and it is useful beyond all the projects that I create using it - beyond the limits of the imagination, beyond the interactivity produced through internet." (Interviewee 3: about a computer)

Personal Identity

Personal Identity involves the individual satisfaction provided by a product, to the point that it reflects the identity and lifestyle of an individual. The sub-groups are described below. It was found that for respondents, 52.8% of childhood objects were classified in this group against 40% of present-day items.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Reflection of Self refers to those products that reflect the user's identity and suit their lifestyles. This property corresponds to 37.7% of childhood items, and only 15.5% of present-day objects. This result shows that during childhood the respondents' need for self-reflection, or to belong to a group is more significant than that at present. It is believed this relates to the process of self-discovery:

- "I like the Barbie because it was a character that marked my childhood and still marks me today. When I was a kid wanted to look like her... I grew up, dyed my hair blonde, I've always liked pink. The Barbie was kind of a DIVA to me (...) I think that because of my introduction to Barbie you can understand why I love this bag right?" (Interviewee 2: on a Barbie purse)

Symbolization of Values involves objects that become personal symbols and to the personification of artefacts. 26.4% of artefactchildhood artefacts fell into this sub-group, and 22.6% of present-day objects. This relationship is described in the following testimony:

- "It was my favorite precisely because the other Barbies are usually all similar. It's all pink dress and stuff but this one was

different: she was rural and not that fashionable Barbie. Her hair was dark. My Barbies were all blondes, and I liked her because she was different". (Interviewee 3: about Barbie Cowboy).

Self-made: those products that have been constructed by the individual. Only 1.9% of childhood objects fell under this sub-group and no present-day items. Thus, for this group of respondents this sub-group had little relevance for attachment. One respondent described the attachment to their handmade customized object as follows:

- "They were just the color of clay and I had the habit of painting them. I used to paint them in my own way. I liked to be able to buy them undecorated and then paint them" (Interviewee 3: about small clay pots).

The sub-group **Interests and Goals** included artefacts that helped respondents pursue their personal interests or achieve some goal. No childhood items were included in this sub-group, against 4.44% of present-day objects. This shows that for this generation, such artefacts are not significant for attachment.

- "I like the camera because, through photography, I can describe and mark important moments for me and others. It is more a more loving relationship than professional, but all this love for photography is related to my adventures." (Interviewee 3: on their camera)

Social Identity

Social Identity: this sub-group involves the adaptation of objects to reflect the individual within their social environment. The four sub-groups were are described below. 41.5% of childhood objects were included in this sub-group compared to 22.2% of present-day objects.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Social Status: corresponds to product quality according to the social aspirations of respondents. 11.3% of childhood objects were included in the sub-group, and only of 4.44% of present-day items. The data indicate that during childhood the need to belong to or appear to be part of a particular group was more important in terms of attachment than is the case today:

"I had three brothers and an older sister, but my older sister was always the "big girl", so because I was younger I played with my brothers. So I loved boys' toys which were the pinnacle for me, because I wanted to associate myself with them; I always wanted to be surrounded by them, which couldn't happen if I was playing with dolls" (Interviewee 5: On a toy car)

Image: the way a person is seen as a result of the use they make of an artefact. 24.5% of childhood objects were included in this sub-group compared to 8.69% of present-day objects:

"When I arrived there with the most colorful marbles and everyone wanted to play with me to win them from me, but I was good at marbles. So I thought it was very good" (Interviewee 5: on marbles).

Union consists of those products that deliver an experience together with other people, such as friends or family. 20.6% of childhood products were classified in this sub-group, against only 11.1% of present-day objects. Thus, for the respondents, use and user experiences were more important in childhood than today.

"Actually I almost failed my third year because of them ... But I couldn't help reading. They were the basis of many conversations I had with my best friend, Tassio. We competed to see who could read the books fastest. What made me like them very much was the bond of friendship they helped make.... These books are awesome.... I recommend reading them with a friend!" (Interviewee 6: About the Percy Jackson books)

Opinion of Others: artefacts that are desired and appreciated by others. 13.2% of childhood artefacts were categorized within this sub-group compared to 11.1% of present-day objects. Thus, in both periods the opinion of others is important for the relationship between individuals and objects:

"But I had no reason not to take it off. At first I only wore it when I went out. Then one day my friend saw me using it and liked it a lot, and from then on I never took it off, well only on a few rare occasions" (Interviewee 7: describing a pendant on a cord).

Form

Form corresponds to the physical elements of a product. Respondents tend to describe the size, colors, shapes, style, etc of objects. For 73.6% of childhood items respondents noted that the aesthetics of artefacts was essential for attachment. 48.9% of present-day products were included in this sub-group - the second highest reason for attachment. Therefore, it is understood that form and aesthetics are key to the attachment, as may be observed in the following testimony:

"My phone. I liked its geometric shapes and its color (also black), I especially liked the fact it was uniform in its thickness and it was completely flat. It wasn't very good, but I loved 'those curves'" (Interviewee 6: on their old cell phone).

CONCLUSIONS

When investigating the affective relations between individuals and products it is possible to identify numerous clues that enable important aspects in the bond of attachment to be understood. This is clear from the analyses of the interviews and questionnaires conducted with the respondent group of young people from the city of Caruaru, Pernambuco State, Brazil. Since this is a qualitative research study, it is possible to identify a strong trend among designers to contribute to projects focused on emotion and feeling. However, it is important to recognize that, as the research involved a small sample in a specific region, it is not possible to generalize the results.

From the results obtained, it was possible to identify numerous attributes relevant to understanding the affective bond between person and object. These features not only help strengthen the relationship between individuals and objects also have a favorable impact on environmental issues. Thus, to the point that users experiences an increased emotional bond with the objects they use they tend to keep them for longer. This results in a decrease in the accumulation of garbage and the frequency with which artefacts are quickly discarded as a result of their ephemerality.

In consequence it was possible to identify and categorize *Reasons* why attachment occurs. Among the most important reasons cited by young people were: Experience, Utilitarian Function and Form, which were most significant for present-day objects. The data illustrate significant differences that point to potentially very distinct patterns. Changes over time, and technological advances, may be crucial in explaining this change. However, some aspects that promote the affective bond are timeless, such as aesthetic considerations (shape, color, etc.), which are important factors to the relationship, as individuals tend to feel attracted to objects that they find beautiful. It was also observed that for young people who are no longer children the experiences of using an object are considered important for the construction of attachment

As has been seen, there are countless possibilities for research aimed at strengthening the emotional bond between people and objects. The focus on such studies is recent, especially in Brazil, where there is still little academic research carried out from this perspective. Therefore, it is both necessary and important to carry out further, more detailed, studies in the field, in order to improve our understanding of the reasons for attachment and to contribute to the important task of strengthening the emotional bond between individuals and objects.

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